

An Investigation on Desilylation of Alkyl and Phenolic Silyl Ethers Using FeCl_3 [†]

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A variety of alkyl and phenolic TBDMS ethers have been efficiently cleaved using anhydrous FeCl_3 in MeOH under mild conditions. It was found that choice of solvent is crucial for the rate of the deprotection of TBDMS ether with FeCl_3 .

The success of any protecting group largely depends upon its stability to acidic or non-acidic reagents, and how easily it can be installed and deprotected. Protection of hydroxyl groups as *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl (TBDMS) ethers is very well utilized in organic synthesis because of its easy installation and general stability to basic and mild acidic reagents^{1,2}. The deprotection of TBDMS ethers is usually done with aqueous acids^{1,3}, fluoride ion¹ and aqueous HF-MeCN⁴. Although tetrabutylammonium fluoride is most popular for deprotection of TBDMS ethers, fluoride ion in aprotic solvents, being a strong base, can affect base-sensitive substrates. Since the strong acidity of aqueous acids is undesirable for acid-sensitive substrates, a variety of other reagents has also been introduced⁵. While working on the enantioselective synthesis of (-)-utenone 1, we required to deprotect the silicon ether in the substrate 2 under a mild condition. Using literature's condition (Dowex-50 Resin, MeOH, 0°, 48 h), we could obtain the product 3⁶ in a maximum of 63% yield. Various literature methods failed to improve the yield of the required product. We then found that ferric chloride in MeOH cleaved the silicon ether of 2 in high yield (92%) under mild conditions⁷ (Scheme 1).

This result was in sharp contrast to an example in a recent paper⁸ where ferric chloride in CH_2Cl_2 cleaved acetals efficiently, but alkyl TBDMS ethers remained unaffected. There is also a report in the literature that $\text{FeCl}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ in

CHCl_3 selectively cleaved acetals, while TBDMS group was intact⁹. However, the use of acetone as a solvent did induce cleavage of TBDMS groups when the reaction was carried out for a longer period of time (18 h). $\text{FeCl}_3/\text{Ac}_2\text{O}$ combination is also known to cleave TBDMS groups¹⁰. It seems that medium is very important for the deprotection of TBDMS groups with FeCl_3 , and to the best of our knowledge, no systematic study has been done so far. In order to clarify the discrepancy of the literature resulting from the different solvents with FeCl_3 , we studied the reaction in detail, and we report here that a medium for deprotection of TBDMS groups is very critical, and MeOH is the best medium for the reaction. We also report that phenolic TBDMS groups can also be cleaved with FeCl_3 in MeOH.

We studied the deprotection reaction of aceanol TBDMS ether with FeCl_3 in several solvents (0.2 M concentration) such as MeOH (98% yield, 15 min), MeCN (95% yield, 15 min), acetone (90% yield, 2 h), benzene (85% yield, 3 h), CH_2Cl_2 (80% yield, 3 h) and ether (90% yield, 5 h). From the above study, it was clear that MeOH was the best medium for the desilylation reaction. Whereas MeCN was an equally good solvent for the desilylation reaction, the reaction was slow in acetone, benzene, CH_2Cl_2 and ether.

Once the solvent study was over, a variety of known alkyl TBDMS ethers were prepared, and their cleavage reaction was studied with ferric chloride in MeOH (Table 1). From Table 1, it is clear that this method offers some advantage in the chemoselective cleavage of TBDMS ethers in the presence of selected functional groups (-MEM, -OAc, -OMe, -OBz). The primary TBDMS ether could be cleaved in the presence of secondary THP ether, secondary TBDMS ether, and acetonide group (Entries 9, 15 and 16). TBDMS ethers were also cleaved with catalytic amounts (10–20 mole %) of FeCl_3 . Under catalytic conditions, primary TBDMS ethers were smoothly deprotected. However, the secondary TBDMS ethers required longer reaction times (1–5 h) for desilylation.

We further extended the method successfully in desilylation of several phenolic TBDMS ethers (Table 2). The desilylation reaction was carried out in MeOH following the above procedure except that the reaction was done at

[†]Dedicated with a great respect to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th birthday.

TABLE 1—CLEAVAGE OF ALKYL TBDMS ETHERS WITH FeCl₃ IN MeOH AT ROOM TEMPERATURE^a

Sl. no.	Substrate	Time	% Yield ^b
1.		15 min	98
2.		15 min	75
3.		15 min	90
4.		30 min	96
5.		60 min	98
6.		4 h	93
7.		3 h	88
8.		90 min	97
9.		10 min	71
10.		15 min	65
11.		60 min	87
12.		3 h	88
13.		3 h	92
14.		3 h	78
15.		2 h	75
16.		12 h	55

^a1 equivalent of anhydrous ferric chloride was used.

^bSecondary TBDMS ether remained intact.

reflux temperature as the reaction was very slow at room temperature. Since the aqueous work-up, in these cases, could also be avoided⁹, the method will enhance the scope of TBDMS protecting groups in phenolic systems as there are only a few methods in the literature for this purpose¹².

In conclusion, we have shown that the choice of a solvent is very crucial for the desilylation reaction of silyl ethers with ferric chloride. We have carried out desilylation reaction on systems with a variable complexities.

Experimental

Cleavage of aliphatic silyl ethers. General procedure : A solution of aliphatic silyl ether (1 mmol) in MeOH (5 ml) was treated with anhydrous FeCl₃ (1 mmol) and the solution was stirred at room temperature until the reaction was complete (Table 1). It was then quenched with aq. NaHCO₃ solution and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, brine, and dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed and the crude product was passed through a small bed of silica gel to provide pure hydroxyl compounds which were found identical to the authentic samples by tlc, nmr and ir.

Cleavage of aromatic TBDMS ethers. General proce-

TABLE 2—CLEAVAGE OF PHENOLIC TBDMS ETHERS WITH FeCl₃ IN MeOH AT 60° FOR 6 h

Sl. no.	Substrate	% Yield
1.		70
2.		70
3.		75
4.		90
5.		95
6.		70
7.		80

cedure : A solution of aromatic TBDMS ether (1 mmol) in MeOH (3 ml) was treated with anhydrous FeCl₃ (1 mmol) at reflux temperature for 6 h. Most of the methanol was then removed on a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure and the crude product was directly chromatographed over silica gel to provide pure phenolic compounds which were found identical to the authentic sample by tlc, nmr and ir.

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